

THE ROLE OF A FAIR SOCIAL POLICY IN ENSURING THE STABILITY OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the principles of conducting a fair social policy in our country, social harmony, solidarity, and interethnic harmony. The history of developed countries shows that it is permissible to take measures aimed at improving the economy along with solving social issues. The reforms being implemented in the social sphere are discussed.*

Keywords: *New Uzbekistan, stability, justice, social policy, social institutions, social agreement, public safety, just civil society, social protest, social protection, state security.*

YANGI O‘ZBEKISTON BARQARORLIGINI TA’MINLASHDA ADOLATLI IJTIMOYIY SIYOSAT YURITISHNING O‘RNI VA ZARURIYATI

Annatotsiya. *Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizda adolatli ijtimoiy siyosat yuritish tamoyillari, ijtimoiy kelishuv, hamjihatlik, millatlararo totuvlik haqida fikr yuritilgan. Rivojlangan davlatlar tarixi iqtisodiyotni yuksaltirishga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlarni ijtimoiy masalalarni hal qilish bilan barobar olib borish joizligini ko‘rsatadi. Ijtimoiy sohada amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar haqida aytib o‘tilgan.*

Kalit so‘z: *Yangi O‘zbekiston, barqarorlik, adolat, ijtimoiy siyosat, jamiyat institutlari, ijtimoiy kelishuv, jamoat xavfsizligi, adolatli fuqarolik jamiyati, ijtimoiy norozilik, ijtimoiy himoya, davlat xavfsizligi.*

РОЛЬ СПРАВЕДЛИВОЙ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются принципы проведения справедливой социальной политики в нашей стране, социальное согласие, солидарность и межнациональное согласие. История развитых стран показывает, что наряду с решением социальных вопросов допустимо принимать меры, направленные на улучшение экономики. Рассматриваются реформы, реализуемые в социальной сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *Новый Узбекистан, стабильность, справедливость, социальная политика, социальные институты, социальное соглашение, общественная безопасность, справедливое гражданское общество, социальный протест, социальная защита, государственная безопасность.*

In our country, this goal has become a priority, and every reform being implemented in our state is aimed at it. Today, as we set ourselves ambitious goals and move towards them, we must pay attention to all areas of society.

One of the areas that plays an important role in the development of a country is the social sphere and the social policy related to it. Since the social sphere encompasses all important parts of social life, it is given great attention in state policy.

In the section entitled “Strong social policy: essence and opportunities” of our esteemed President's “Strategy of the New Uzbekistan”, the following idea is presented: “Transforming New Uzbekistan into a country of happy people, satisfied with their lives, into a comprehensively developed social space is the main goal of our reforms in this direction.” Today, a wide range of news is being made to realize this goal put forward by our President.

Large-scale reforms aimed at realizing human rights and interests are underway in all spheres of life in our country. The consistency of such democratic reforms, sustainable economic growth In the period of ensuring and further development of free market relations, it is important to systematically implement measures to solve social problems and ensure the stability of the population's well-being. The history of developed countries shows that it is permissible to carry out measures aimed at improving the economy along with solving social issues. This practice strengthens the relationship between society and the state and has a positive impact on sustainable development. Thus, social problems and conflicts in developed countries are eliminated, and any emerging issues are resolved through mutual social agreement between state and social institutions. Otherwise, social discontent and disagreements will intensify, and factors that undermine public safety, peace and tranquility of the people will increase. In this sense, the principles of conducting a fair social policy, which are the basis for the path of renewal and development of our country, are aimed, first of all, at ensuring social agreement, harmony, interethnic harmony and solidarity.

The fact that every person in our society deeply feels the essence of democratic changes, realizes that thanks to reforms they can fully realize their potential, and most importantly, aligns their vision with the aspirations of society and the state is a very important factor in achieving the ambitious goals we have set for ourselves.

The referendum on the adoption of the new Constitution demonstrated the unity and solidarity of our multinational people and became a vivid example of their determination to renew our society, becoming one body and soul with our state, on the basis of the norms of our fundamental law, and ensuring that our tomorrow is better than today. Constitutional changes have been reflected in the socio-political, socio-economic image of the achievements of our state and society, which have been formed as a result of the reforms that have been taking place

rapidly in recent years. As our Honorable President emphasized, “The norms of the Constitution have determined the new strategic goal of state building - building a social state and increasing the well-being of the people on the basis of the principles of social justice and social solidarity, comprehensively supporting the vulnerable segments of the population, and creating conditions that allow every person to live a peaceful and dignified life.”

Most importantly, these norms further strengthen the foundations of a democratic, just civil society. In such a society, state agencies and employees serving at any level of state power, pursuing the interests of the people, serve to implement human rights and freedoms established in our Constitution and the laws adopted on its basis, and in this activity rely on the principles of social justice and legality. Focusing on the main aspect of social justice, the goal of state agencies at all levels is to satisfy the needs and desires of every citizen, regardless of nationality, race, or social origin, which is reflected in the constitutional and legal norms that have always prioritized the humane and humane qualities of our people above all else, and that people are truly respected. Another important issue. As enshrined in constitutional norms, our state, in the interests of the people, carries out reforms in all aspects of our life, including in the social sphere, first of all, they are aimed at ensuring justice, that is, at fully realizing the rights and freedoms of every person without any discrimination, at guaranteeing the well-being of the population, a decent and stable lifestyle in families, which are the primary unit of our society.

Today, ensuring a decent, free and prosperous life for the population of our country, and creating all the necessary conditions for the full use of the rights and opportunities of every person are among the priority tasks on the path to building a new Uzbekistan.

Social policy, its implementation mechanisms also include creating conditions for increasing the labor activity of citizens, their broad involvement in entrepreneurship. This, in turn, plays an important role in preventing a sharp decline in the standard of living of the population, unjustifiably large differences in income and living standards, ensuring peace and stability in society, and strengthening confidence in reforms. If inequality of various forms increases in any state and there are factors that allow this, social stability is undermined. The emergence of sharp differences between social classes creates the basis for the emergence of contradictions and internal conflicts in society. Therefore, the most important task of a democratic state is to prevent factors that cause social conflicts, resolve existing difficulties, and improve people's living conditions. In such conditions, civil servants are required to understand the essence of reforms very well. Otherwise, social injustice will be violated, corruption will increase, and the already difficult situation of a person suffering from a particular social issue may be aggravated, serious social instability may arise, and civil peace, society and state security

may be threatened. It is clear that thanks to the ongoing reforms and the selfless work of our people, Uzbekistan's place and position in the world arena are increasingly increasing.

Special Opportunities It would not be an exaggeration to say that the current changes taking place in Uzbekistan have begun a new history for the country. After all, the huge innovations taking place in our country in the socio-economic, political and other spheres are literally ensuring the integration of our state with the world community.

Today, our country is inviting the world to itself, moving from a closed approach to an open pragmatic policy. Such an approach, of course, requires reforming the existing procedures and bringing them into line with world standards.

Within the framework of the strategy of actions, we plan to convey to the world community the content and essence of a completely new social policy being implemented in our country, as well as to determine the prospects for mutual cooperation and partnership between state bodies and other institutions of civil society in the field of social protection of the population.

It also demonstrates Uzbekistan's openness, readiness for active, practical cooperation, and the study of international and foreign experience in solving problems related to social protection of the population. Our achievements in ensuring human rights and freedoms, freedom of speech and religious belief, and gender equality are being consistently strengthened in cooperation with influential international organizations.

The commitment of the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan to social justice and the protection of the interests of people in need of social protection determines its position as the left wing of the country's political forces.

Comprehensive measures to develop the social sphere are aimed, first of all, at strengthening social protection and health care of citizens, providing the population with affordable and high-quality medicines, increasing employment and real incomes of citizens, expanding the construction of affordable social housing, and providing comprehensive support to persons with disabilities.

Social policy remains one of the most priority areas of state policy in our country. The targeted nature of social support allows for assistance to be provided to each person in need, taking into account their real needs. Particular attention is paid to ensuring that no person in this category is left out.

A fair social policy is an approach to every reform aimed at improving the well-being of the population from the perspective of justice, not neglecting any strata of society, creating equal opportunities and conditions for them, and helping them find their place in society.

The main tasks of a fair social policy implemented in our state are: to economically and legally guarantee the realization of the rights of every person to work and receive education; to develop a mechanism for social protection for all segments of the population, primarily those in need of social protection; to prevent unemployment; to create a social insurance system; to prevent a sharp decline in the standard of living of the population; to create measures to ensure the well-being of the population, etc. The implementation of these tasks will lead to a high level of future development.

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